

APPENDIX S1. Examined images of herbarium specimens for which the collector, island of occurrence, or determination was uncertain. Each sheet with one or more specimens is a single row entry. Rows are numbered (No.) and sorted by taxon as determined here and then current herbarium (Hb.). Numbering of multiple specimens mounted on a single sheet follows the markings on sheets. The text of original labels is transcribed, with semi-colons separating individual labels. Ellipses indicate symbols, illegible writing, or other content specified in brackets. Specimen phenology is indicated in parentheses. Notes on collectors are from Urban (1902) unless otherwise indicated.

No.	Taxon	Hb.	Historic Hb.	Label Text and Phenology	Notes
1	<i>Eugenia cordata</i> var. <i>cordata</i>	B-W	n/a	on folder: 9555; Polyandria Monogynia, Myrtus cordata . . . [diagnosis] Swartz prod. 78., Habitat in India occidentali . . . ; on sheet: Vahl. W., M. cordata, 1. (fl)	Barcode B -W 09555 -01 0.
2	<i>Eugenia cordata</i> var. <i>cordata</i>	C	Hornemann	Myrt. cordata Sw. ex Ind. occid.—Sw. (fl)	n/a

No.	Taxon	Hb.	Historic Hb.	Label Text and Phenology	Notes
3	<i>Eugenia cordata</i> var. <i>cordata</i>	C	1/3: M. Vahl 3/3: Liebmann	1/3: Myrtus cordata West (fl, fr); 2/3: h: in Ste. Cruce, L, Eugenia, Myrtus ramiflorus (fl, fr); 3/3: Myrtus? ex Ind. occid. (fl)	F. M. Liebmann collected on St. Croix and possibly Puerto Rico 1841; on Cuba 1843.
4	<i>Eugenia cordata</i> var. <i>cordata</i>	C	N. Hofman Bang	Myrtaceae Eugenia cordata; Myrtus cordata, ex India occidentali, . . . Lund (fl)	n/a
5	<i>Eugenia cordata</i> var. <i>cordata</i>	C	Schumacher	Eugenia, Ind. occid., D Benzon (fl)	P. E. Benzon collected on St. Croix, St. John, and St. Thomas 1817–1848.
6	<i>Eugenia cordata</i> var. <i>cordata</i>	C	1/4: M. Vahl 2/4: M. Vahl 3/4: Liebmann 4/4: M. Vahl	1/4: <i>Pflug s.n.</i> (see text); 2/4: cordata, Dedit Dr West (fl); 3/4: Eugenia ramiflora (fr); 4/4: Myrtus cordata (fl)	Pflug collected on St. Croix at the end of the 18th century. Liebmann (see #3).

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7	<i>Eugenia cordata</i> var. <i>cordata</i>	C	N. Hofman Bang	Myrtus cordata . . . Doni Vahl (fl)	n/a
8	<i>Eugenia cordata</i> var. <i>cordata</i>	C	1/2: Schumacher 2/2: Schumacher	1/2: Myrtus cordata . . . h. in S. Cruce (fl); 2/2: <i>Ryan s.n.</i> (see text)	J. Ryan collected on St. Croix, St. John, and Montserrat during the second half of the 18th century. His brother collected on Trinidad.
9	<i>Eugenia cordata</i> var. <i>cordata</i>	C	1/2: Liebmann 2/2: Liebmann	1/2: Myrtus cordata, Eugenia sessiliflora, ex Ind. occid. (fl); 2/2: Myrtus cordata Sw., ramiflora, Ind. occid. (fl)	Liebmann (see #3).
10	<i>Eugenia cordata</i> var. <i>cordata</i>	C	S. Drejer	Ind. occid. W., Dr Ravn, Myrtus cordata (fl)	P. Ravn collected on St. Croix, St. John, St. Thomas, and Vieques 1819–1839.

No.	Taxon	Hb.	Historic Hb.	Label Text and Phenology	Notes
11	<i>Eugenia</i> <i>cordata</i> var. <i>cordata</i>	C	M. Vahl	Dr West (fl)	n/a
12	<i>Eugenia</i> <i>cordata</i> var. <i>cordata</i>	C	Schumacher	<i>Eugenia sessiliflora</i> , Myrtus <i>cordata</i> ... (fl)	n/a
13	<i>Eugenia</i> <i>cordata</i> var. <i>cordata</i>	C	Schumacher	<i>Eugenia sessiliflora</i> , Myrtus <i>cordata</i> , Ryan Lam ... (fl)	Ryan (see #8).
14	<i>Eugenia</i> <i>cordata</i> var. <i>cordata</i>	C	n/a	1/2: Myrtus <i>cordata</i> , ex Antillis ... (fl); 2/2: ded. Ryan, <i>Eugenia sessiliflora</i> (fl)	Ryan (see #8).
15	<i>Eugenia</i> <i>cordata</i> var. <i>cordata</i>	G-DC	Puerari	<i>Eugenia ramiflora</i> (fl)	Barcode G00658524.

No.	Taxon	Hb.	Historic Hb.	Label Text and Phenology	Notes
16	<i>Eugenia cordata</i> var. <i>cordata</i>	L	n/a	No. 18, Eggers Fl. Ind. Occ. Exsicc. Ser. 2, Myrtac.; 18. <i>Eugenia lateriflora</i> W. (fl)	No. L.2508325.
17	<i>Eugenia cordata</i> var. <i>cordata</i>	M	Schreber	<i>Myrtus cordata</i> Swartz; No. 13 <i>Eugenia</i> ; <i>Eugenia?</i> <i>cordata</i> Dc., St. Lucia? St. Thomas? <i>Crudy?</i> (fl)	Crudy collected in the Bahamas and on St. Thomas and St. Lucia before 1810. Barcode M-0137708.
18	<i>Eugenia cordata</i> var. <i>cordata</i>	MA	n/a	<i>Myrtus cordata</i> Swartzii, 2088; <i>Plantae Novae Hispaniae</i> . a Sessé, Mociño, Castillo et Maldonado lectae (1787–1795–1804). <i>Eugenia cordata</i> (Sw.) DC., No. 2088 (st)	Probably collected by H. West as evinced by handwriting. Could also have been collected by Sessé & Mociño on Puerto Rico 1796–1797 (Blanco and Puig-Samper 2003). Barcode MA 603224; Chicago Natural History Museum Negative No. 47166.

No.	Taxon	Hb.	Historic Hb.	Label Text and Phenology	Notes
19	<i>Eugenia</i> <i>cordata</i> var. <i>cordata</i>	P	Antoine Laurent de Jussieu	Myrtus cordata Sw., Ste. Croix. antillis, dedit . . . Vahl 1799 (fl)	No. P00678225.
20	<i>Eugenia</i> <i>cordata</i> var. <i>cordata</i>	P	A. N. Desvaux	<i>Eugenia cordata</i> . . . [citations], Myrtus— . . . [citations], habitat in Antillis. (fl)	Barcode P05238849.
21	<i>Eugenia</i> <i>cordata</i> var. <i>cordata</i>	P	Poiret, Moquin- Tandon, E. Cosson	Myrt. cordata Sw. (fl)	Barcode P05238855. On sheet with <i>Myrciaria cordata</i> O.Berg.

No.	Taxon	Hb.	Historic Hb.	Label Text and Phenology	Notes
22	<i>Eugenia cordata</i> var. <i>cordata</i>	S	n/a	No. S08-855: <i>Eugenia cordata</i> , Sw. scripsit; <i>Eugenia cordata</i> DeCand., <i>Myrtus cordata</i> Swartz., Ind. Occid.: Swartz (fl); No. S13-23361: <i>Eugenia sessiliflora</i> DC. var. (fl)	n/a
23	<i>Eugenia cordata</i> var. <i>cordata</i>	S	n/a	<i>Myrtus cordata</i> Sw.; dedit. Hornemann (fl)	No. S08-856
24	<i>Eugenia cordata</i> var. <i>cordata</i>	WAG	n/a	Familie: Myrtac., Geslacht: <i>Eugenia</i> , Soort: <i>cordata</i> DC. (fl).	No. WAG.1115167. Possibly collected by C. Le Gallo.

No.	Taxon	Hb.	Historic Hb.	Label Text and Phenology	Notes
25	<i>Eugenia cordata</i> var. <i>caribaea</i> ?	C	1/2: M. Vahl 2/2: M. Vahl	1/2: Myrtus lateralis (Plinia), ded. Dr ... (fl); 2/2: Plinia, ded. Dr ... [same as 1/2] (fl, fr)	Tentatively annotated as <i>Eugenia cordata</i> var. <i>sintensii</i> by Urban.
26	<i>Eugenia cordata</i> var. <i>caribaea</i> ?	LINN	n/a	Myrtus ramiflora, Nevis rupibus, Masson (fl)	F. Masson collected in the Lesser Antilles and on Jamaica 1779–1781.
27	<i>Eugenia sessiliflora</i>	C	1/2: Hornemann 2/2: Liebmann	1/2: habeo sub nom. Eugen. foetida (fl); 2/2: <i>Liebmann s.n.</i> (see text)	Liebmann (see #3).
28	<i>Eugenia sessiliflora</i>	C	n/a	In monte ... ?, 5/47, Leg. Oersted (st)	A. S. Oersted collected on St. Croix, St. Thomas, and Jamaica and in the Lesser Antilles 1845–1846.

No.	Taxon	Hb.	Historic Hb.	Label Text and Phenology	Notes
29	<i>Eugenia sessiliflora</i>	P	L. Cl. Richard, (Guyanensi- Antillanum)	No. 29. <i>Eugenia venosa</i> . . . [description], Euge. lateriflora? Vahl. Symb., non <i>Myrtus cotynifolio</i> . . . frequens in sylvalis montosis Ste. Crucis et St. Joannis (st)	Barcode P05238180.
30	<i>Eugenia sessiliflora</i>	P	L. Cl. Richard (Guyanensi- Antillanum)	29. <i>Eugenia venosa</i> (fl)	Barcode P05238182.
31	<i>Eugenia sessiliflora</i>	P	n/a	. . . <i>Eugenia cotinifolia</i> Jacq., lateriflora, isle ste croix (fl)	Barcode P05238183

LITERATURE CITED

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